

AQUARIUS Website (D7.3)

Seascape Belgium

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1. Summary

This document constitutes the "AQUARIUS Website" as Deliverable 7.3 and outlines the specifications regarding website design and technology, the Key Performance Indicators and supports and facilitates the implementation of the AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.1).

2. Overview and objectives

The AQUARIUS project website (<https://aquarius-ri.eu/>) is the central repository for project information, research infrastructure (RI) catalogue, training materials, project resources and storytelling, and serves as the gateway to the AQUARIUS Transnational Access (TA) Platform.

Objectives of the website:

1. Introduce and promote the opportunities offered in the project's TA Funding Calls and stimulate responses to these calls.
 - a. Showcase the available research infrastructures via an attractive online catalogue.
 - b. Provide clear and concise explanatory content about the TA Funding Calls, the challenge areas, submission and selection process, feature the case studies and provide the link to the TA platform.
 - c. Develop and maintain the AQUARIUS Training Hub as an easy navigable repository of training material, highlight training opportunities for early career researchers and facilitate applications to these.
 - d. Link to the AQUARIUS data dashboard (ADD).
2. Promote uptake of results and opportunities, particularly the TA Funding Calls and the selected projects outputs, training opportunities and exploitable results by end-users from all sectors and within all target audiences, by providing success stories and engaging updates on progress.
3. Ensure the following designated targets are met:
 - a. 3000+ visits to the site.
 - b. 500+ downloads of the infographic describing the AQUARIUS catalogue of services and infrastructures available.
 - c. 300+ views of digitally stored training products and dissemination outputs.

3. Requirements

3.1. Business requirements

The AQUARIUS website is developed to meet the requirements of the project, as follows:

- The website is publicly available and is GDPR compliant.
- The website supports the above objectives, particularly the support of a seamless connection to the AQUARIUS TA Platform (TAP).
- Clearly located 'call to action' buttons will link visitors to newsletter subscription, contact forms, application forms and the TAP to increase the opportunity for impact of the project through stakeholder engagement.
- The site is maintained with regular updates and the timely resolution of reported bugs.

- The soft launch of the website coincided with the AQUARIUS kick-off meeting (April 2024). The site is officially launched by 31 August 2024 and will be hosted for a period of four years beyond the end of the project (February 2032).
- The site is both content and functionally ready to support PPC campaigns (Pay-per-click) increased traffic.

3.2. User requirements/Target Audiences

The AQUARIUS project has identified five different target audience groups, further detailed in the AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) (D7.1). For the purpose of understanding the requirements of users for the website, these groups have been clustered into two main categories.

Primary Group: Scientists and technical experts

Trained scientists and technical experts, including early career researchers, working in academia, industry, citizen science groups, public bodies and NGOs as the main target group of the TA Funding Calls and technical training opportunities. This group will also encompass research infrastructure providers with an interest in the AQUARIUS RI portfolio, best practices and future vision for integration of RI services.

Members of this group will visit the site with the key goal of obtaining information on the RI, TA Funding Call information, information on technical training and related opportunities, and exploitable results. Their main priorities are assumed as: viewing the catalogue of RIs, reading instructions related to the Funding Calls, accessing the TA Portal, accessing the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard, accessing training material and relevant scientific and technical outputs.

Secondary Group: Wider Stakeholders

Interested users from civil society, industry, policy and wider society.

Members of this group will visit the site for project information, training material, results, relevant outputs and to read success stories. It is also assumed they will be interested in viewing the RI catalogue and in learning how AQUARIUS is relevant to wider society and contributes to the objectives of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters.

Commonalities

Both primary and secondary stakeholder groups comprise tech-savvy individuals who may be accessing the site via mobile phones. They do not want to spend time exploring the site through endless scrolling. It is assumed they are busy professionals who will appreciate clean navigation to quickly and intuitively shepherd their way to the desired information.

4. Design and Specifications

Best practice website design and development are being deployed in the initial construction of the site and will be applied throughout its regular maintenance and expansion as the project progresses and new information is generated.

4.1. Information Design

The site architecture (Figure 1) is based on the business/project and user requirements defined above to support a clean, user-friendly experience featuring intuitive navigation and easy access to information about the project, the research infrastructures, the TA calls and platform, training materials and opportunities, data and exploitable results.

Figure 1. The AQUARIUS site map

Top menu items are named with familiar terms for the primary identified audiences. These visitors will know what to find in these sections. Drop-down links are used for larger sections offering quick navigation to desired information (see also Figure 2). A search button on top of the page improves the user-navigation and quick searches for information.

Bright call-to-action buttons, contrasting with background colours for visibility, are used to direct visitors to more information and or to support project requirements, such as access to the TA Platform(TAP). As seen in Figure 2 below, a specific call-to-action button will support the KPI of 500 downloads of the project infographic.

Social media icons on the top invite the user to follow the AQUARIUS community on X, LinkedIn, Instagram and Facebook. The envelope icon provides the user with an email address to get in contact with the AQUARIUS team.

Pages are laid out simply with graphic elements sized appropriately to minimize the need for scrolling and to allow the information to take center stage. Prime real estate is reserved for priority information and identified user goals.

Figure 2. An internal page of the AQUARIUS website demonstrating the drop menu and call to action buttons.

Figure 3. The AQUARIUS research infrastructures catalogue page of the website, including "sort" functionality, interactive map, links to individual research infrastructures and "call to action" buttons.

4.2. Visual Design

The visual design of the website is based on the attractive brand identity established for the AQUARIUS project. It evokes a welcoming environment with eye-friendly colours and easy to read fonts.

Figure 4. The AQUARIUS "News and Events" page features news articles and events information, with the function to pin important items at the top of the list.

Friendly conceptual graphics will be used to convey complex scientific concepts, and professional photographs and video clips will also be featured in news sections and throughout the catalogue to visually demonstrate the features of the Research Infrastructures.

4.3. Tech Specifications – Functionality & Performance

4.3.1. Compatibility

The website and domain name are hosted on secure European servers at Combell (based in Belgium). The hosting environment uses the latest PHP and SQL technology and will be further updated as the project progresses. The content management system (CMS) used to update the content of the website is Wordpress Elementor. This CMS is flexible and easy to use by various members of the Seascope Belgium team to ensure content can be updated quickly. The website will follow maintenance on regular time intervals to ensure security and functionality so users can easily navigate to the content they require.

4.3.2. Privacy Policy/GDPR

A cookie banner has been integrated on the website so users can set their preferences to be tracked by Google Analytics. The website contains a privacy policy and cookie policy to inform users of how their data is processed and their rights, according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). An additional privacy policy has been added to the newsletter subscription page referring to the tool being used to store the newsletter contacts.

4.3.3. SEO

During the design and development phase Search Engine Optimization (SEO) has been considered. Every page has been tagged with keywords and a clear meta description about what to find on the page. Additional efforts will be made to optimize the SEO as the content develops.

4.3.4. Accessibility

The AQUARIUS website will strive to be compliant with the Web Accessibility Directive ([Directive \(EU\) 2016/2102](#)) and its aims to make public sector websites and mobile applications more accessible, reducing barriers for developers of accessibility-related products and services (such as text readers for the sight-impaired). By providing meta tags to graphics and ensuring blockers are removed, content on the site will be accessible to a broader audience, thus helping to increase AQUARIUS' potential for impact.

4.4. Content Standards

The content standards of the website will align with the Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) (D7.1). All content will be published in English and harmonized for a more general, non-technical audience with concepts explained and acronyms only used when accompanying a full name, unless continuously used in a piece of text. Infographics and icons will be used to convey complex concepts.

The tone may vary for specific stakeholder groups, i.e. there will be assumed prerequisites of technical knowledge for some material, i.e. training. However, as per the CDP, it will be clear, factual, concise and professional. It will avoid over-use of jargon, and not be overly complicated, gimmicky, reductive, patronizing, or inappropriate. The layout of text will be scannable and clean, avoiding long blocks of text.

5. Ongoing Maintenance

5.1. Reviews and development

Initial design and development of the AQUARIUS website is taking place in a collaborative manner between WP1-WP6 and WP7, in order of priority. Design concepts, mock-ups and the sitemap have been submitted for review and approval with the different WPs. This process will continue post the official delivery of the website for any major updates or new sections.

A website bug reporting log has been created and content and functional bugs are entered when they are identified. The WP7 team will conduct targeted checks as part of the initial development cycle and periodic reviews throughout the project duration based on the editorial calendar defined in the CDP.

5.2. Update Plan

The AQUARIUS site is a dynamic platform for ongoing communication of project information and will be updated regularly, working with project partners to achieve the relevant milestones and deliverables, and to highlight project outputs, activities and opportunities in a timely manner.

6. Promotion Plan

Ongoing promotion of the website will involve:

- Links and QR codes on communication material being disseminated at conferences and events. These links will either lead to the homepage or in some cases to specific areas of the website.
- Social Media invitations to visit the site.
- Links in email campaigns and newsletters.
- Implementation of SEO metadescriptive data and tags on webpages as described above.

In support of the Transnational Access Funding Calls, the website will be prepared to receive traffic drawn from the two outreach campaigns; one per Call, including the pay-per-click (PPC) campaigns to ensure broad outreach and successful participation of the targeted audiences.

7. Conclusion

This document outlines the objectives, requirements, design and specifications, maintenance and promotion of the AQUARIUS website. The website will be a key platform for AQUARIUS to enable the project to meet its objectives and deliver impact.